

Indigenous Epistemologies and Supernatural Figurations in *Thakumar Jhuli*: A re-reading of selected Bengali folk narratives

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Abstract: *Indigenous folk tales are a form of cultural archive that shaped imagination, nurtured creativity, and reinforced the ethical sensibilities of the inhabitants of the land. Indigenous folk tales gives the knowledge of the past; it is the bearer of cultural heritage. Thakumar Jhuli, written by Dakshinaranjan Mitra Majumder is regarded as one of the most celebrated collections of folktales in Bengali literature. Thakumar Jhuli gives the reader the knowledge about the past, its cultural practices, and its indigenous food habits, represents the society. In the eastern regions of the world, folklores were the medium of instruction, through which one generation could pass on their rituals and heritage to the next generation. The supernatural imagery in the stories invokes not only a sense of fear and horror but also the stories indulge the readers into deep thinking. In folklore, supernatural elements usually stimulate the imaginative faculties of readers while simultaneously shaping collective consciousness of the natives. Through fantastical imagery, Thakumar Jhuli presents the supernatural as a realm that exists beyond rational explanation and scientific interpretation. The cultural and supernatural dimensions of Thakumar Jhuli reveal folk culture as representative of ancestral beliefs and traditions. Blending imagination with moral instruction, Thakumar Jhuli tales exemplify how folklore transcends temporal boundaries, and continues to inspire critical thought and cultural continuity in contemporary discourse.*

Keywords: *Culture, Folklore, Literature, Moral, Supernatural.*

Introduction: The *Thakumar Jhuli* series is compiled by Dakshinaranjan Mitra Majumdar; the tales occupy a unique position in Bengali folk literature. The function of folktales is to blend the indigenous ethos with a vibrant world of supernatural fantasy. The stories of *Thakumar Jhuli*, reflect on the collective consciousness of a society that is deeply rooted in domestic values, moral justice, and spiritual endeavour. The indigenous elements and supernatural elements together form the narrative core of these tales; these elements shape the moral fabric and cultural authenticity. The indigenous elements in these tales are deeply connected with the socio-cultural environment of nineteenth-century Bengal; it reflects on the everyday life and beliefs of rural Bengal. The presence of kings, queens, priests, farmers, and village women in folktales, points towards a socio-cultural realism that mirrors a pre-modern agrarian community. The language in these tales is simple, rhythmic, and is deeply interwoven in colloquial idioms, which helps in preserving the flavour of oral storytelling. Famous folklorist A.K. Ramanujan in *Folktales from India* opines that a folktale is a text in poetic form that carries some of its cultural contexts within it; the folktales are also a travelling metaphor that finds a new meaning with each new telling (Ramanujan, Preface, pp.15). These supernatural elements elevate the simple tales into moral allegories. The ordinary is transformed into an extraordinary moral trials; the supernatural figures are sometimes symbolic extensions of rewarding moral good and punishing evil. To analyse the theme of Supernatural and the role it plays, the literary examples of supernatural are picked up from those four tales which will help understand the idea of the folk traditions in the narratives of Bengal.

The tale of two sisters and the role of Mother Moon:

In Thakumar Jhuli series, the story of “Two Sisters” presents a narrative of ‘Dukhu’ and ‘Sukhu’, the daughters of a weaver from two different wives; this story functions both as a moral allegory and as a cultural repository, as it preserves the values concerning virtue, kindness, and justice. The story’s central character is a supernatural force, the Mother Moon, whose role is to reward good and punish evil characters. The narrative of the story begins with the death of the weaver, who leaves behind his two wives and two daughters. The elder wife, after the death of the weaver, grabs all the property and hides it for the future of herself and for her daughter. But the younger wife and her daughter spent their days in extreme poverty, and they used to make their living by weaving saree from the thread left behind by the weaver. One day the younger wife went to take bath in the river keeping the cloth outside, in the sun to dry, but a misfortune occurred when a gust of wind blew the cotton away, and Dukhu, the daughter submerged in extreme sorrow upon the sudden loss from their means of living, as the money that comes from weaving is their sole income source. Upon seeing Dukhu’s sorrow, the gust of wind took pity on her and instructed her to follow the direction of the wind to get back the cotton.

The quest of Dukhu to find the cotton takes her on a long journey until she witnesses the supernatural character of the narrative, the mother moon. The journey helps her to evolve as a better human being, and for that she should be rewarded. Dukhu, towards the beginning of her journey, encountered a cow; she was generous and helped the cow by providing her the food, hay and water. After that, Dukhu met with a banyan tree that pleaded her to get it rid of the climbers that she happily agreed and set the tree free. The next one to meet her is a large tree, that stops her and pleading her to clean the heap of rubbish at the base of its trunk. Further in the journey, she also meets a horse who was in need of a bundle of grass; she helped everyone and refused none. In helping each of these figures, Dukhu affirms her intrinsic kindness, humility, and help others selflessly.

Finally, towards the end of the story, Dukhu arrived at a cottage, where she met an old woman sitting and weaving. The lady is the mother moon who had pretended earlier to be the wind that snatched her cloth to examine her spirit. But the moon mother was actually a very soft-hearted self who was overwhelmed by Dukhu’s sincerity, and she guides her through a series of symbolic choices. Dukhu consistently demonstrates her modesty and restraint, by preferring the torn towel to the lavish ones, choosing simple food over abundance, and selecting the smallest box of cotton among many other ornate alternatives. As per the instructions, no sooner had she immersed herself in the water than she was transformed into a beautiful maiden, but uncertain of this result, Dukhu took another dip, and this time her whole body was covered with gold jewellery. Upon remembering the lady’s instruction, she went back to the cottage and, out of many types of overflowing food, she found comfort with the simple food items. When finally she asked for her cotton, the lady instructs Dukhu to go back to her hut and choose a box of cotton from the shelf, but Dukhu, the honest being, chose the smallest one from the other varieties. On her way back home, the ones she had helped return their favour by various means. Ultimately, she returned home and explained everything to her family, the stepmother got envious of Dukhu and asked Sukhu to immediately follow her sister, but the greed and jealousy destroyed her true self and turned Sukhu into a filthy being. The contrast is sharply drawn when Sukhu, urged by her moth-

er to replicate her sister's fortune, embarks on the same journey but with greed as her guiding force. Unlike Dukhu, Sukhu neglects other's emotions, she disregards the pleas of animals and trees, who were asking for her help and chose extravagance at her every juncture. Her self-centred choices culminate not in reward but in filth and humiliation, reinforcing the tale's central moral theme that, it is not external appearances or material desires but inward goodness that determines one's fate.

The figure of the 'Mother Moon' functions as an arbiter of cosmic justice within the narrative. Her role exemplifies the folkloric motif of the supernatural being who rewards virtue while punishing vice. Thus, the mother moon serves the role of a supernatural being who pays individuals based on their merit and goodwill. The tale of Dukhu and Sukhu confirms that the ethical principles of virtue would always shine amidst adversity, restoring the ethical balance. Through these symbolic encounters, supernatural mediation, and moral contrasts in these tales, justice is ultimately meted out according to one's merit and goodwill.

Princess Kalabati and the tale of Bhutum and Budhu:

The tale of "Princess Kalabati," is taken from the *Thakumar Jhuli* series, it presents a wide range of characters, beginning with a king, who has seven wives, but all of whom were childless. These wives, while performing their regular rituals upon the riverside, encounter a divine sage, who gives the eldest queen roots and leaves of a tree and advised her to divide the herbs with the other six wives, the herbs will strengthen the possibility to become mothers and bear a son from their womb. But when the queens came to divide the herb, the fourth and last queen got only the dregs of the magical herb and as a result, they gave birth to an owl and a monkey, respectively. The mothers of Owl and Money were discarded from the palace and were soon turned into a maid and a cow dung girl. As the narrative evolves further, the other princes grew up as handsome princes, but the owl prince 'Bhutum' and monkey prince 'Budhu' began to suffer and had to lead a hardworking life in order to sustain. Eventually in the course of action, Budhu undertakes a journey towards the kingdom of Hell, and there he meets with an old woman, who sat huddled in a corner stitching a quilt; upon seeing Budhu, she calls for the soldiers and ties him into a dark room. He pretends to be dead and in the next morning in the hope of not getting noticed uses trick to escape. But the kingdom of Hell appears superstitious, as it never has been told to him. Inside the hell lived a beautiful maiden who at the end gets married to Budhu. Later Princess Kalabati, the maiden of the kingdom gets wedded to Budhu and Bhutum got married to Princess Hira-bati. 'Hell' serves as a very important place that though is a reflection of supernatural world and its entities, yet it helps Prince Bhutum and Budhu to get their deserved prizes. The indigenous elements in the tales present the cultural and social realities of Bengal. The portrayal of the Hell kingdom, while fantastical, embodies the moral geography of folk imagination, a space where human endeavour interacts with cosmic justice. The "old woman stitching a quilt" and other domestic details retain the oral flavour of grandmother's tales, typical of *Thakumar Jhuli*, where the ordinary blends seamlessly with the miraculous.

'Kiranmala' the protagonist, symbolizing female leadership:

In the story of "Kiranmala" from *Thakumar Jhuli* tales, the central character is Kiranmala, who has to suffer adverse situations in the course of the narrative. The beginning of the story happens when we encounter a rich king getting married with one of the three sisters from a village, leading to the arousal of jealousy in the minds of the other two sisters. The happy family of the king gets destroyed when

the sisters tricked the members of the palace into believing that the children are dead and must be submerged into river, they managed to put the children in a basket and push them into the face of death. The siblings were soon survived by a maiden and taken to a priest, where they were fostered. But as fate intervened, the two brothers got abducted by some supernatural forces, and the central character Kiranmala undertakes a journey alone towards the Maya mountain to rescue her brothers. The name “Maya” suggests illusion; the supernatural nature of the mountain makes it impenetrable; the arrival of Kiranmala, to the mountain was followed by some luring music and turning back to it would suggest inevitable death, as the human body will then be turned into a stone. The sword and the arrow & bow become the metaphor for their life, and the moment the sword would break, it will signal towards the death of her brothers. As the sword breaks, she decides to bring back her brothers. Kiranmala proves to be a stout, passionate, and courageous princess. She defeated the power of the supernatural, as she not only disregarded the luring evocation in her way but also overcame all other adversity and reached the bell, the ringing of which brings back life of her brothers as well as other princes captivated there. The end of the story is significant as the king recognizes his children and brings the queen back from exile, and they lived happily ever after. In Kiranmala, we find a woman, who is struggling with her fate to overcome the power of the supernatural with her compassion, love, and faith. The supernatural elements of ‘Maya’ are depicted in a negative sense, tending to harm human individuals.

The story “Kiranmala” from *Thakumar Jhuli* mentions the harmonious coexistence of supernatural imagination combining with indigenous moral values that are central to Bengali folk tradition. Kiranmala’s triumph over the traps of ‘Maya’ symbolises an assertion of human agency; it is a testament to the enduring faith that righteousness and devotion can conquer mystical malevolence. Indigenous elements in the narrative reaffirm the supernatural motifs in the cultural contexts. Kiranmala’s heroic actions stand in contrast to the passive female archetypes of the classical tales; she embodies an indigenous form of feminine strength, her character is shaped by compassion, moral righteousness, and unyielding faith. There is also an interplay between these supernatural and indigenous dimensions as “Kiranmala” transcends its fairy-tale boundary to deliver a distinctly cultural message of unending strength of courage, which ultimately helps restore the balance in the narrative. The story’s conclusion where recognition, and reunion follow struggle evokes the cyclical resolution typical of Bengali moral folklore, celebrating both human strength and divine justice.

The story of Lalkamal-Neelkamal and the Demon:

The story of Lalkamal and Neelkamal began with a kingdom and a king having two wives, one of whom is a demon in disguise. Each wife bears a son: Kusum (the good queen’s son) and Ajit (the demon queen’s son). The two boys were close friends, and this caused hatred in the demon-queen because she secretly desired Kusum, the step son as her food, but the friendship of his son to Kusum was preventing her from fulfilling her desire. The demon queen uses black magic to weaken the good queen until she dies. Later, someday at night, the demons invade the palace and seize Kusum; while the king is held motionless by the queen’s spell, the demon devours Kusum. Ajit wakes and strikes the demon and a golden ball comes from the demon’s mouth. As Ajit intends to rebel, the demon queen loses her mind and swallows her own son, Ajit, and soon an iron ball also comes out of her throat.

The queen collects the gold and iron balls, buries them in a remote bamboo grove, and drifts home. A farmer while cutting bamboo in the jungle finds two eggs, one red/gold and one blue/iron, frightens by those, he discards them. The eggs hatch, producing two crowned and armed princes; the reborn Kusum and Ajit, was then named Lalkamal and Neelkamal respectively.

The twin princes then come to another kingdom where the local people were terrorized by demons; rulers keep losing ministers to the fiends. The local king promises his twin daughters Ilavati and Leelavati along with his kingdom to anyone who can set him free. Lalkamal and Neelkamal fight with the demons, and they hide and trick the demons using their cleverness. Neelkamal and Lalkamal defeats the demons of that land, and liberates the kingdom. They marry the princesses and become twin king of the land. The information reaches to the evil demon queen that the demons has been slain. She sends her messengers disguised as soldiers to ask for oil to cure the king's disease; the two young kings promise to get the oil. On their journey they take shelter in a holy fig inhabited by two talking Bengama birds; the brothers give the birds a few drops of human blood as per their need and to express their gratitude, the birds carried the brothers across mountains for seven days till they find the edge of the demons' realm. Here, the Bengama birds, act as supernatural helpers: *"In the tree lived a pair of talking Bengama birds." The Bengama Birds worked as mediators between the human and other-worldly realms.*

In the demon-land, the demon grandmother suspects Lalkamal and tests him with an iron beans. Lalkamal swaps and passes the test; proves himself and soon were accepted. When the brothers infiltrate the demon-land, Neelkamal acquires a golden box containing two hornets, which were the keys to the demons' lives- *"Inside the box were two hornets, Jiyonkati and Moronkati. Jiyonkati held the key to the lives of thousands of demons, and Moronkati held the key to the life of the demon queen"* (Majumdar, 80). The mutilation of these demon like figures in the narrative further leads to the cosmic justice: *"Neelkamal then pulled off two legs of the hornet Jiyonkati. Immediately, the legs of all the demons fell off... Using his sword, Neelkamal cut off the hornet's head. Immediately, all the demons were beheaded."* (80) Neelkamal mutilates Jiyonkati by pulling off legs, limbs, and head and each injury metaphorically signified the other demons losing their legs, hands, and finally being beheaded. The boys take the demon grandmother's head with them and also bring Moronkati to use against the demon queen. The princes send the demon grandmother's head to the evil queen. The queen rushes to confront them; Lalkamal kills Moronkati and opened the box where there was the hornet controlling the queen's life, *"On hearing of the arrival of the demon queen, Lalkamal opened the gold box and killed the hornet, Moronkati. Instantly, the demon queen fell on the floor, stone dead."* (80) The king's disease is cured immediately after the charm of the demon queen is lost. The two princes return to their father's kingdom, unify their father's realm with the one they won through marriage, and live happily ever after.

Society defines the rewards for heroic deeds as in the story, the king promises to his kingdom that, *if the twin princes could save his kingdom, he would marry off his beautiful twin daughters, Ilavati and Leelavati to them and even offer them his kingdom.* Victory is not only measured by the slaying of the demons but also by securing some marriage alliances that will help the brothers in establishing leadership. *Neelkamal and Lalkamal* reveal how folktales interweave the supernatural

spectacle with the social meaning. The demon queen is not just supernatural; she is enmeshed in royal households, in stepmother dynamics, and in rivalry over succession. Her evil is a radical exaggeration of social conflicts: jealousy, maternal competition, and kinship intrigues. Society becomes the stage on which supernatural evil manifests.

The importance of Folktales and its cultural significance:

Folktales are an intimate part of one's culture, but culture is not only limited to one's region; instead, the span of culture is undefinable as it has existed from time immemorial, first in oral culture and slowly evolved with the existence of scriptures. Matthew Arnold, in his famous book *Culture and Anarchy*, defines culture as "the best that has been thought and said." Generally, in South Asian folktales, 'marriage' and 'kingdom' are the common rewards for heroic acts. A.K. Ramanujan also notes that many male-centered tales end with the hero winning a princess and kingdom. The primary focus for a hero is not limited to killing demons; he should also get social recognition and be valued and accepted; he should also get a princess as his winning possession. Society, represented through the characters like the king or the people, should have few promises for the kingdom that the heroes must fulfill. Comparative folklore theorists like A.K. Ramanujan, and Vladimir Propp, in their respected works clarify how these elements align with broader patterns in South Asian and global folkloric tradition. Vladimir Propp, in *Morphology of the Folktale*, identifies stable "functions" (like villainy, departure, acquisition of magical agent, and resolution) as well as characters fulfilling the roles of (hero, donor, helper, etc.) According to Propp's structuralism theory, folktales follow a sequence of "functions," such as the departure for the quest, the donor's test, following the hero's victory. The sequence of these functions tends to be consistent across variants. A.K. Ramanujan's observations on Indian folktales are that many tales are "male-centred" and involve the quests of hero, magical helpers, stepmothers or rivals, and social restoration through marriage and kingdom.

The supernatural elements enhance the storytelling qualities, the magical beings creates dramatic tensions throughout the narrative enhancing the charm and interest in the minds of the listener. The folktales tales are filled with wonder, they provide allegorical learnings that allow audiences to interpret life, found its meanings, helps establish morality, and make subtle changes in human behaviour. The supernatural elements in Indian folktales are not merely decorative, instead they are integral to the structure and themes of the narrative, they emphasizes on the cultural resonance of the land. Within these cultural context, *Thakumar Jhuli* tales not only entertain the readers of all ages but also instruct the young minds by embedding values of humility, selflessness, and moral rectitude into the social consciousness. The presence of supernatural beings like ogres, talking birds, and celestial maidens, reflects what Tzvetan Todorov called the "fantastic" in literature; the tension between the natural and the supernatural exists together, and the belief and the scepticism coexist, collecting all fragments as a whole.

Conclusion: In *Thakumar Jhuli* tales, the magic underscores moral laws; divine intervention becomes the vehicle through which justice is ultimately restored; the supernatural does not subvert the reality; instead it reinforces the cosmic and ethical order. What makes the tales of *Thakumar Jhuli* particularly distinctive is its indigenous realism and supernatural wonder. The tales preserve not only the mythic imagination of Bengal, but also the psychological and cultural

truths of the native people. The synthesis of the indigenous elements with the supernatural forces, transforms the tales of *Thakumar Jhuli* into more than just a collection of fairy tales; and it became a mirror to society. By invoking both local realism with magical transcendence, Dakshinaranjan Mitra Majumdar's *Thakumar Jhuli* tales, succeed in creating a folkloric moral universe where human endurance, compassion, and faith triumphs over illusion and evil.

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